

1 **Title: Chromatin immunoprecipitation and high throughput sequencing of SVCV-infected**
2 **zebrafish reveals novel epigenetic histone methylation patterns involved in antiviral**
3 **immune response**

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25 **Abstract**

26 Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) and high throughput sequencing (ChIP-seq)
27 have been used to assess histone methylation (epigenetic modification) dynamics within the
28 internal organs of zebrafish after spring viremia of carp virus (SVCV) infection. Our results
29 show H3K4me3 up-methylation in gene promoters associated with innate immune response
30 during the first 5 days after SVCV infection. Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis
31 confirmed up-methylation in 218 genes in the “immune system process” category. In particular,
32 the promoters of interferon (ifn), interferon stimulated genes (isg), Toll-like receptors (tlr) and
33 c-reactive protein (crp) multi gene sets were marked with the permissive H3K4 methylation.
34 Higher histone 3 methylation was associated with higher transcription levels of the
35 corresponding genes. Therefore, the evidence presented here suggests that transcriptional
36 regulation at the promoter level of key immune genes of the interferon signaling pathway and c-
37 reactive proteins genes can be modulated by epigenetic modification of histones. This study
38 emphasizes the importance of epigenetic control in the response of zebrafish to SVCV infection.

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42 *Keywords: zebrafish, SVCV, histone methylation, ChIP-seq, innate immunity*

43 1. Introduction

44 In mammalian models viral infection is known to activate gene expression over a period
45 of time. Virus-induced transcriptional activation can be achieved by histone modification in the
46 promoter regions, an epigenetic mechanism probably related to trained immunity, a type of non-
47 specific immunological memory that provides protection against reinfection (1). Many
48 methylation events have been positively correlated with gene activation. In particular, tri-
49 methylation of histone H3 lysine 4 (H3K4me3) is one of the histone modifications widely
50 associated with genes undergoing active transcription (2, 3). It is currently unknown whether
51 such mechanism may exist in zebrafish, although viral infection does induce large-scale changes
52 in host transcription in zebrafish (4).

53 The development of biotechnological methods such as ChIP and next generation
54 sequencing provides us with the tools needed to better understand some of the epigenetic
55 mechanisms of zebrafish response to viral disease at the genome level. In the ChIP assay, the
56 DNA coupled to the modified histone is precipitated with the corresponding antibody to
57 H3K4me3. This DNA is then purified and sequenced, which provides a quantitative measure of
58 regions in the genome that were enriched in a particular methylation pattern after infection.
59 Such genome-wide studies on fish epigenetics have contributed to a better understanding of the
60 response to viral pathogenesis and the development of new prophylactic and therapeutic
61 strategies to control viral diseases in aquaculture (5, 6).

62 To investigate the molecular mechanisms underlying cyprinid fish response to viral
63 infection we have chosen zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) because it has become an established model
64 for teleost fish immunology studies where complete genome sequence and gene annotation are
65 required. Furthermore, microarray analysis of immune-related responses to experimental
66 infections of zebrafish with spring viremia of carp virus (SVCV) and viral hemorrhagic
67 septicemia virus (VHSV) have been reported (7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12). SVCV causes an acute
68 disease in cyprinid fish species with outbreaks typically in spring both in farmed and wild fish
69 with a serious impact on the aquaculture industry of common carp and koi (13).

70 Here we present data that reveal the modulation of the epigenetic methylation pattern of
71 chromatin during SVCV infection of zebrafish. Samples from the four experimental groups
72 (non-infected control, 1, 2 and 5 days post SVCV infection) were analyzed. The analysis of the
73 data showed that SVCV infection was associated with changes in the histone 3 methylation in a
74 large number of genes with a typical role in immune signaling pathways and host pathogen
75 response. Our findings suggest that epigenetic reprogramming may be an underlying
76 mechanism in fish to achieve an enhanced protective response to subsequent exposure to
77 pathogens.

78

79 **2. Materials and methods**

80 2.1. Cell culture and virus.

81 The zebrafish embryonic fibroblast ZF4 cells were purchased from the American Type
82 Culture Collection (ATCC number CRL-2050). ZF4 cell lines were maintained at 28 °C in a 5%
83 CO₂ atmosphere in RPMI Dutch modified (Gibco, Invitrogen corporation, UK) cell culture
84 medium buffered with 20 mM HEPES and supplemented with 10% fetal calf serum (Sigma, St.
85 Louis, USA), 1 mM piruvate, 2 mM glutamine, 50 µg/ml gentamicin and 2.5 µg/ml fungizone.

86 The spring viremia of carp virus SVCV isolate 56/70 was grown in the ZF4 cell line at
87 22°C by using the same cell culture media mentioned above except for 2% fetal calf serum.
88 Supernatants from SVCV infected ZF4 cell monolayers were harvested at 7 days p.i. and
89 clarified by centrifugation at 4000 r.p.m. for 30 min and kept in aliquots at -70 °C. SVCV titers
90 were measured by a methylcellulose plaque assay (8, 14). Briefly, serial dilutions of SVCV
91 were used to infect ZF4 cell monolayers in 24-well plates for 1.5 hours. Then, the media were
92 removed and each well was covered with a solution of 2% methylcellulose (Sigma) in RPMI
93 2% fetal calf serum. Plates were incubated at 22 °C for 5 days. Finally, the methylcellulose
94 overlay was removed and the wells stained with crystal violet to visualize plaques due to virus-
95 induced lysis.

96

97 2.2. Infection of zebrafish with SVCV

98 Animal trials procedures were approved by the local government ethics committee on
99 animal experimentation (Dirección General de Agricultura, Ganadería y Pesca, Generalitat
100 Valenciana) and registered under permit number 2016/VSC/PEA/00182. Zebrafish (40 fish,
101 0.35-0.4 g average body weight) were exposed by bath immersion to a dose of SVCV (2×10^4
102 pfu/ml) for 90 minutes at 21°C. At 1, 2 and 5 days post infection the fish were sacrificed by
103 overexposure to the anesthesia (MS-222, Sigma) and whole head kidney, liver, spleen and heart
104 of 3 fish per treatment were extracted and pooled. Two pools were generated for each
105 experimental condition (6 fish total). The procedure is outlined in supplementary figure 1.
106 Mortality was monitored for 15 days.

107

108 2.3. Chromatin Immunoprecipitation

109 Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) was performed using the Imprint® ChIP Kit
110 (Sigma) following the instructions described by the manufacturer. Samples were placed in tubes
111 containing 1% paraformaldehyde (PFA) and fixed for 20 minutes. After this time, glycine (1.25
112 M) was added for 5 minutes to stop the reaction followed by centrifugation and wash with
113 phosphate buffered saline to remove PFA. The washed samples were sonicated to shear the
114 chromatin in small fragments, centrifuged and aliquots analyzed by agarose gel electrophoresis
115 to verify DNA cleavage into 200-500 bp fragments. ChIP was performed using anti-trimethyl
116 histone H3 (Sigma). Once the DNA was immunoprecipitated, the binding reaction was reversed
117 and the DNA was purified using the columns provided by the Imprint® ChIP kit.

118

119 2.4. Sequencing of immunoprecipitated chromatin (ChIP seq).

120 Chromatin precipitated DNA was sent to Bioarray Co. (Elche, Spain) for high-
121 throughput sequencing. SVCV-infected and control uninfected samples (2 pools of 3 fish each)
122 were sequenced. The four experimental groups were: uninfected control; SVCV-1dpi (days
123 post-infection); SVCV-2dpi and SVCV-5dpi. The genetic libraries were built using the
124 NEBNext Ultra II DNA kit for genetic libraries for Illumina (Lucigen, England). The libraries
125 were then sequenced using an Illumina NextSeq500 in 2x75 mode. Sequence reads were

126 subjected to a quality control by the program FastQC and a standard filtering by the program
127 Trimmomatic. Total number and average length of sequence reads are shown in Figure S2. An
128 alignment of the readings to the *Danio rerio* GRCz10.85 genome version was then performed
129 using the Bowtie2 program. Data analysis of the ChIP seq experiment was performed using the
130 MACS program. This program employs a computational algorithm that identifies transcription
131 factor / chromatin / histone binding genome regions (promoter sequences) from the ChIP seq
132 data. Sequencing data was provided in an excell spreadsheet containing the list of the
133 corresponding genes, gene identification in the UNIPROT database, number of reads, and the
134 relative fold increase versus uninfected control.

135

136 2.5. Analysis of ChIP sequence data to identify differentially methylated gene promoters.

137 Initially we performed a crude cleansing analysis of the data, eliminating those readings
138 that were not assigned to any specific gene. Once this process was completed for each of the
139 samples, we proceeded to global gene analysis and verification of the gene sets that were
140 enriched in expression. The analysis was performed by two methods: a) global analysis of all
141 the genes obtained and using the application of GESTALT
142 (<http://www.webgestalt.org/option.php>). b) Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) application
143 (<http://software.broadinstitute.org/gsea/index.jsp>).

144 To determine the gene sets enriched in the list of genes obtained by sequencing, we used
145 the GESTALT gene cluster analysis tool. This list of genes was generated for each of the
146 experimental groups (non-infected, SVCV-1dpi, SVCV-2dpi, SVCV-5dpi), including only the
147 annotated genes.

148 To perform the Gene Set Enrichment Analysis, the 12500 genes were analyzed using
149 the gene sets (GS) described in Estepa and Coll, 2015 (Table S1). The list of unique genes and
150 values was ranked by the t-test statistic metric (similar results were obtained using the Signal-
151 to-Noise ratio statistic) and the ranked list was used to calculate Enrichment Scores (ES) by
152 comparing the following zebrafish phenotypes: SVCV-1d versus Control, SVCV-2d versus
153 control and SVCV-5d versus control. The GSEA calculated individual gene enrichment scores

154 (ES), overall ES for each GS and finally normalized ES (NES) to correct for the number of
155 genes present in each GS. As suggested by GSEA, the most stringent cut-off value of $p < 0.05$
156 value was used for NES significance. The FDR method was chosen because only FDR corrected
157 for both gene size and multiple hypothesis (null distribution from 1000 random gene
158 combinations per GS). Because the zebrafish GS were derived from human/zebrafish
159 orthologous pathways and that might be inaccurate, the Leading Edge Gene Analysis (LEGA)
160 was used to search for empirically clustered genes (GS/LEGA matrixes) indicative of novel fish
161 GSs.

162

163 2.6. RNA isolation and gene expression analysis by RT-qPCR.

164 For total RNA extraction the E.Z.N.A. HP Tissue RNA kit (Omega Bio-tek) was used
165 following the manufacturer's instructions. DNase treatment was done in order to eliminate
166 residual genomic DNA using TURBO™ DNase (Ambion, Thermo Fischer Scientific Inc.),
167 following the manufacturer's instructions. RNA samples were stored at -80°C until use. One
168 microgram of RNA, as estimated by a Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo-fisher
169 Scientific, Inc), was added to the cDNA synthesis reaction with Moloney murine leukemia virus
170 (M-MLV) reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen Corporation, UK). Quantitative PCR (qPCR) was
171 performed using the ABI PRISM 7300 System (Applied Biosystems) Primers used for
172 quantitative real-time PCR analysis are listed in Table S3. The reaction was performed in a total
173 volume of $20\mu\text{L}$, comprising $2\mu\text{L}$ cDNA reaction mixture, 900nM each primer, $10\mu\text{L}$ of SYBR
174 Green Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) and $6\mu\text{L}$ of water. The cycling conditions were 50°C
175 for 2 min, and 95°C for 10 min, followed by 40 cycles at 95°C for 15 s, and 60°C for 1 min.
176 Expression of gene transcript levels was calculated by the $2^{-\Delta\text{Ct}}$ method (15) where ΔCt is
177 determined by subtracting the Ct value from the eukaryotic translation elongation 1 alpha (ef1a)
178 gene, used as endogenous control, to the target Ct value. Every sample was run in triplicate.

179

180 2.7. Statistical analysis.

181 Statistical analysis was performed using the GraphPad Prism v5.0 software. To compare
182 the datasets of the different treatments with their respective uninfected controls, Tukey tests
183 were used. When applicable, significant differences were represented as asterisks (*, **)
184 indicating $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively.

185

186 **3. Results**

187 3.1. Infection of zebrafish with SVCV.

188 To further characterize zebrafish as an experimental model for SVCV infection a bath
189 immersion challenge was performed as described earlier (8, 14). Under our experimental trial
190 conditions symptoms of SVCV disease started at 3 days post-infection (dpi), with external
191 hemorrhages in the mouth, gills, lateral skin and fins found on infected fish (Fig.1A). Survival
192 in the SVCV-infected group went down to 10% after 14 days whereas in the control group only
193 one dead fish was recorded whose death was not infection-related (Fig.1B). Replication of
194 SVCV was monitored by N gene RNA quantitation by real-time RT-PCR (RT-qPCR). SVCV-N
195 RNA increases with time after infection (Fig.1C), indicating a viral productive infection in the
196 diseased fish.

197

198 3.2. Genes with differential methylation in histone 3 after SVCV infection.

199 At each time point after SVCV infection two samples made of a pool of the internal
200 organs from 3 fish each were analyzed. Briefly, chromatin was extracted, fragmented and
201 immunoprecipitated with the anti-H3K4me3 antibody. Immunoprecipitated DNA was
202 sequenced and genes were annotated with UNIPROT using the *Danio rerio* genome as a
203 reference. The number of reads of each annotated sequence was converted to fold-enrichment
204 over the non-infected control group. Genes with a fold-enrichment value ≥ 1.5 over the non-
205 infected control group were considered differentially methylated genes (DMGs). There were
206 11907 unigenes with a fold-enrichment value ≥ 1.5 in the SVCV-infected groups compared to
207 the control groups ($p < 0.05$). A Venn diagram was drawn to show the DMGs in organs of

208 SVCV-infected fish at different time points (Fig.2A). The number of genes with the H3
209 trimethylation mark remained constant within the experiment time frame (5 days).

210 Functional classification and Gene Ontology (GO) analysis of enriched genes were
211 performed. Genes were grouped into three categories: biological processes, cellular component
212 and molecular function. We focused our attention to the first category (biological processes),
213 which includes the genes involved in the response to the stimulus (Fig. 2B). A subset of 218
214 genes with fold-enrichment values ≥ 1.5 in the three SVCV groups (1, 2 and 5 dpi) was
215 identified within the “immune system process” keyword in UNIPROT Biological process
216 category (Fig.S4).

217 Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) showed a general response to external stimuli and
218 stress already at 1 dpi (Table 1). At later times (2 and 5 days after SVCV infection) the activated
219 gene sets have a more concrete profile associated with adaptive and innate immune responses to
220 a viral infection. Thus, there was a rapid promoter activation in genes of the Toll-like receptors
221 (*tlr*), interferon (*ifn*), transforming growth factor beta (*tgfb*) and tumor necrosis factor alpha
222 (*tnfa*) signaling pathways, amongst others. A particularly interesting group of genes, c-reactive
223 proteins (*crp*) showed the H3K4me3 mark. CRPs are serum proteins synthesized in the liver and
224 released to blood during inflammation or infection with pathogens. At 5 dpi the *crp* and *nitr*
225 (novel immune-type receptor) gene families were the only gene sets significantly enriched in the
226 H3K4 methylation (Table 1).

227 KEGG pathway analysis of DMGs identified the Toll-like receptor signaling pathway
228 enriched in all SVCV-infected groups (Table S2).

229

230 3.3. Activation of immune-relevant genes.

231 We took a closer look to the H3K4 methylation status of those genes with an especially
232 relevant role in immune response to viral infection. The fold-increase values of the H3K4me3
233 mark over non-infected controls are shown in Fig. 3.

234 All the Toll-like receptors (*tlr*) gene promoters were activated already at 1 dpi and
235 maintained more or less constant levels of methylation up to 5 dpi, with the exception of *tlr1*

236 that continued increasing at 2 and at 5 dpi. The activation profile of pro-inflammatory cytokines
237 gene promoters (*tnfa*, *il1b*, *il6*) was also enhanced in the SVCV-infected fish samples.

238 SVCV infection led to a change in the methylation of interferon genes promoters: there
239 was a rapid activation of *ifnphi3* at 1 dpi followed by a decline. Coincidentally, the stimulator of
240 interferon genes (*sting*) showed the same pattern as *ifnphi3*. the Interferon regulatory factors
241 (irf) *irf3* and *irf7* were up-methylated from day 1 post-infection. With respect to interferon-
242 stimulated gene promoters (ISGs) the myxovirus resistance (*mx*) gene promoters were up-
243 methylated from 1 dpi onwards. Other ISGs genes such as the gene encoding the reovirus-
244 induced protein *Gig2* was also up-methylated at constant levels from 1 to 5 dpi as well as the
245 proteins containing tetratricopeptide repeats (IFITs) *ifit8* and *ifit14* were found up-methylated.
246 The *rsad2* (also called *viperin*) gene promoter showed H3K4 methylation enrichment increasing
247 with time.

248 Interestingly, of all examined genes the most highly up-methylated genes were those
249 encoding for c-reactive proteins (*crps*), showing a maximal 9.9-fold H3K4me3 enrichment at 5
250 dpi (Fig.3F), which is in good agreement with the GSEA data.

251 Other selected genes associated with host responses to viral pathogens such as
252 antimicrobial peptides beta-defensin and hepcidin, were also examined, both of them showing
253 some degree of up-methylation.

254

255 4.- RT-qPCR analysis of immune-relevant genes expression.

256 Trimethylation of the lysin 4 in histone H3 should result in active regulation in the
257 promoter region of a gene with a corresponding increase in its transcription levels. To further
258 substantiate the ChIPseq observations, RNA from the SVCV-infected zebrafish internal organs
259 was isolated and gene expression analyzed by real-time RT-PCR (Fig.4).

260 Despite the intrinsic high variability of in vivo experiments, a time-dependent pattern of
261 gene expression could be drawn for every gene. Thus, we found that all the selected up-
262 methylated genes showed transcriptional activation. The expression values over non-infected
263 controls of the selected genes were in agreement with the ChIPseq analysis. For instance, those

264 genes previously associated with response to viral infection in fish such as *tlr3* or *tmem173*
265 (*sting*) were up-regulated at all times post-infection. Other genes involved in innate immune
266 activation pathways like *mavs* and in inflammatory responses (*il1b*, *il6*) were also up-regulated
267 from 1 to 5 dpi. Similarly, genes directly related to the interferon response (*irf3*, *ifnphi1*, *gig2*,
268 *rsad2*) were also transcriptionally activated, particularly *irf7* and *mxab* as well as the
269 antimicrobial peptide beta-defensin (*bdef2*) gene were also up-regulated from 2 to 5 dpi. The
270 expression of *ifn* and *mx* genes displayed ever increasing values matching the SVCV N gene
271 RNA measurements, likely reflecting the progression of the disease. All the *crp* genes exhibited
272 increasing transcription from day 1 to 5 post-infection: *crp2* and *crp6* showing a strong increase
273 at the latest time (5 dpi) while *crp1*, *crp3*, *crp4* and *crp7* showed sustained activation.

274 Taken together, RT-qPCR data confirmed that H3K4me3 histone methylation patterns
275 were associated with the up-regulation of innate immune signaling pathways genes caused by
276 SVCV infections.

277

278 4. Discussion

279 ChIP sequencing is an effective method to identify transcriptionally activated genes and
280 therefore obtain information on the organism response to a given stimulus, such as pathogen
281 infection. To our knowledge this is the first study on the changes in histone methylation in the
282 promoters of genes induced in virus-infected zebrafish. This work was aimed to get a better
283 understanding of the host factors involved in response to SVCV infection, and perhaps
284 identifying those epigenetic marks that would lead to an enhanced immune response upon a
285 secondary infection.

286 Bath immersion was our choice on the way of SVCV infection because it resembles the
287 natural infection route. Zebrafish infected with SVCV by bath immersion (8, 14) show
288 characteristic symptoms of the disease (11) and experience mortality. In other works the
289 challenge was done by intraperitoneal injection of the virus (16). This may lead to some
290 inconsistencies compared to bath immersion data regarding the exact pattern and time-course of
291 gene expression after viral infection (8).

292 In the present study, ≈ 12000 genes showed differential methylation of histone H3 in
293 those samples taken from zebrafish infected with SVCV. Data analysis identified GO terms
294 related to host defense mechanisms (“immune system process”) and KEGG pathways (Toll-like
295 receptor signaling) involved in innate immune response. GSEA analysis revealed that only two
296 gene sets (*crp*, *nitr*) were enriched in differentially methylated genes at 5 dpi. This may reflect
297 the host gene expression going back to basal levels after an early response to the virus
298 challenge.

299 Increased levels of H3K4me3 in the promoter region should correlate with enhanced
300 transcription and stimulation of the marked genes. Other system-wide evaluations of virus-host
301 interactions (such as microarray data) have shown a large impact of viral infection on the fish
302 transcriptome (4, 5, 6, 8, 17). Viral infection of fish stimulates the production of type I IFN, one
303 key factor in mounting an antiviral response to protect the host from disease. Rhabdoviruses are
304 powerful inducers of interferon gene expression in cyprinid fish, both in vitro and in vivo (18,
305 19, 20, 21). Our data show the transcriptional activation of *ifnphi3* which is in accordance with
306 other authors’ findings (4, 9, 22). Upstream of the interferon genes in the interferon response
307 pathway, the interferon regulatory factors (*irf*) constitute a family of transcription factors that
308 regulate the transcription of interferon genes. We found a close relationship between activation
309 of promoters and gene expression for *irf3* and *irf7* in SVCV-infected fish that correlates with the
310 up-regulation of *ifnphi3* (23, 24). IRF3 and IRF7 are known to be involved in response against
311 rhabdovirus infection in fish (25) with *irf3* reaching a peak of expression earlier than *irf7* (26)
312 similar to what we found in here. IRF3 has also been associated with the enhancement of the
313 antiviral gene *gig2* expression in fish (27). Gig2 is an important antiviral protein in fish,
314 providing resistance to SVCV infection when overexpressed in zebrafish cells (27).

315 In addition to *gig2*, other genes that have been proven to play an important role in
316 antiviral response in fish such as *rsad2/viperin* (28, 16) or *sting* (29) were rapidly up-methylated
317 after SVCV infection. The interferon inducible proteins IFITs have been proposed to have an
318 antiviral role in fish (30). Several *ifit* genes were found transcriptionally active in the SVCV-

319 infected group, with *ifit8* and *ifit14* showing the highest fold increase over the non-infected
320 controls.

321 One relevant interferon-stimulated gene, *mx*, showed an increasing transcriptional
322 activation over time in SVCV-zebrafish. Up-regulation of *mx* expression after rhabdovirus
323 infection of cyprinid fish has been previously found in other experimental trials (8, 21).

324 Similar to mammalian Toll-like receptors (TLRs) piscine TLRs play a key role in the
325 initial recognition of the virus alerting the fish about danger and triggering immune responses
326 (31). As stated before, promoters of genes in the Toll-like receptor signaling pathway were
327 activated upon SVCV infection. In particular, *tlr2* and *tlr3* have been found to be rapidly
328 induced in kidney of SVCV-infected common carp although their levels decreased after 5 days
329 (26).

330 Toll-like receptors involved pathways activate transcription of proinflammatory
331 cytokines: *il1b*, *il6* and *tnfa* gene promoters were up-methylated in the SVCV-infected samples
332 compared to non-infected samples at all time points. The *tnfa* gene is usually expressed at an
333 early stage after virus infection of fish (32), while *il6* has been associated with immune
334 responses of fish to virus challenge (33). Here, a rapid inflammatory response was triggered by
335 SVCV in zebrafish internal organs.

336 One multigene family not usually associated with host antiviral defense has been
337 identified in this work: c-reactive proteins (*crp*) confirming a previous report (4) describing a
338 possible relationship between the CRPs and virus infection. CRPs were discovered to increase
339 their circulating levels in blood in response to bacterial infection (34). Previous studies by our
340 group have hinted that CRPs may have an antiviral role in fish (4, 35, 36). In connection with
341 the up-regulation of *il6* found in here, this interleukin has been associated with stimulation of
342 *crp* expression in zebrafish before (35).

343 In summary, we have explored the promoter-activating epigenetic modification
344 H3K4me3 in response to SVCV infection in zebrafish. The histone methylation occurs rapidly,
345 in the first 24 hours after infection. This is in agreement with other reports of epigenetic changes
346 being established as fast as 5 hours post-stimulus (37). The maintenance of a hypermethylated

347 (up-regulated) chromatin profile along time could help to establish a memory of the innate
348 immune system, similar to what has been termed “trained immunity” (38). This state of
349 readiness of the innate immune system would render the host more resistant to a subsequent
350 infection (39, 40). Another of the landmarks of mammalian trained immunity is the enhanced
351 expression of proinflammatory cytokines similar to what has been described in here. This study
352 provides novel evidence for the role of epigenetics in the immune response of teleost fish. In the
353 future, the modulation of other transcription associated marks (either methylation or acetylation
354 of histones) may be investigated to get a comprehensive view of the epigenetic reprogramming
355 phenomenon. This knowledge will likely contribute to the understanding of the molecular basis
356 of disease control in aquaculture.

357

358

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368

369 **Conflict of interest**

370 The authors declare that there are no potential competing interests that may influence
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372

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485 **Figure captions**

486 Fig.1. SVCV challenge of zebrafish.

487 A) Hemorrhagic symptoms induced by SVCV infection. The images show representative fish
488 taken at day 8 post challenge. B) Cumulative percent survival of zebrafish infected with SVCV
489 by bath immersion. C) Viral load in SVCV-infected fish examined by RT-qPCR using specific
490 primers for the N gene. Mean \pm SD (n= 5 fish).

491

492 Fig.2. Genes targeted by the H3K4me3 histone modification in SVCV-infected zebrafish.
493 Number of genes with fold-increments \geq 1.5 compared to non-infected fish. A) Venn Diagram
494 of genes displaying differential H3K4me3 signal at different time points after infection. B)
495 GESTALT analysis showing the “biological processes” functional categories with activated
496 genes. N= number of genes.

497

498 Fig.3. Changes in H3K4 methylation of immune-related genes. Relative increase profiles over
499 the control group in response to SVCV infection. A) TLRs; B) Inflammatory cytokines; C)
500 Interferons and interferon regulatory factors; D) Interferon-stimulated genes (ISGs) E)
501 Antimicrobial/antiviral genes; F) C-reactive proteins.

502

503 Fig.4. Changes in the expression profiles of several genes in zebrafish infected with SVCV.
504 Transcript levels of selected genes were evaluated by qRT-PCR and expressed as number of
505 fold increases over the non-infected control group. Mean \pm SD data from 3 fish are shown
506 (*p<0.05; **p<0.01). A) Selected immune-related genes. B) C-reactive proteins multigene
507 family.

508 **Table 1.** GSEA analysis. List of enriched gene sets in the SVCV-infected groups.
 509

SVCV	Gene set	SIZE	NOM p-val	FDR q-val
1 dpi				
	<i>TLR</i>	9	0.06629834	1.0
	<i>CYTOSOLIC DNA-SENSING PATHWAY</i>	14	0.15240642	1.0
	<i>ALPHA6-BETA4 INTEGRIN SIGNALING</i>	12	0.13477089	1.0
	<i>HOM</i>	15	0.17032968	1.0
	<i>APOPTOSIS</i>	16	0.19473684	1.0
	<i>IFN</i>	17	0.19261214	1.0
	<i>TGF-BETA SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	14	0.21899736	1.0
	<i>CHK</i>	6	0.22424242	1.0
	<i>IGS</i>	7	0.27019498	1.0
	<i>COM</i>	8	0.34472933	1.0
	<i>MEASLES</i>	34	0.3358396	1.0
	<i>RIG-I-LIKE RECEPTOR SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	22	0.36503857	1.0
	<i>APOPTOSIS MODULATION BY HSP70</i>	17	0.4458763	1.0
	<i>PROTEIN PROCESSING IN ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM</i>	30	0.4275	1.0
	<i>TOLL-LIKE RECEPTOR SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	34	0.4508816	1.0
	<i>NATURAL KILLER CELL MEDIATED CYTOTOXICITY</i>	21	0.4716495	1.0
	<i>TGFB RECEPTOR SIGNALING WIKIPATHWAY</i>	39	0.5252525	1.0
	<i>PROTEASOME DEGRADATION</i>	30	0.56171286	1.0
2 dpi				
	<i>CRP</i>	7	0.014778325	0.07955655
	<i>TLR</i>	9	0.1131579	1.0
	<i>IGS</i>	7	0.23684211	1.0
	<i>TGF-BETA SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	14	0.23626374	1.0
	<i>MAPK SIGNALING PATHWAY WIKIPATHWAY</i>	10	0.31989247	1.0
	<i>APOPTOSIS</i>	16	0.32448378	1.0
	<i>EGFR1 SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	43	0.27972028	1.0
	<i>ALPHA6-BETA4 INTEGRIN SIGNALING</i>	12	0.33854166	0.942
	<i>TOLL-LIKE RECEPTOR SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	34	0.41025642	1.0
	<i>HOM</i>	15	0.4469914	1.0
	<i>PROTEASOME DEGRADATION</i>	30	0.47727272	1.0
	<i>TOLL-LIKE RECEPTOR SIGNALING WIKIPATHWAY</i>	33	0.62903225	1.0
	<i>IFN</i>	17	0.61904764	1.0
	<i>JAK-STAT SIGNALING PATHWAY</i>	11	0.61403507	1.0
5 dpi				
	<i>CRP</i>	7	0.0	0.0023
	<i>NITR</i>	6	0.9756098	0.9797

510

511

512 **Table S 1:** Gene Sets designed by Dr. Julio Coll (INIA, Madrid)

513

keyword, name	genes	KEGG pathway name	genes	WIKI pathway name	genes
<i>Antimicrobial peptides, amp</i>	9	<i>Antigen processing and presentation</i>	23	<i>Alpha6-beta4 integrin signaling</i>	36
<i>Apoptosis, apo</i>	36	<i>Apoptosis</i>	25	<i>Apoptosis wikipathway</i>	49
<i>Complement, com</i>	36	<i>Bacterial invasion of epithelial cells</i>	35	<i>Apoptosis modulation by hsp70</i>	13
<i>Cluster differentiation antigens, cdi</i>	281	<i>B cell receptor signaling pathway</i>	42	<i>B-cell receptor wikipathway</i>	94
<i>Chemokines, chk</i>	45	<i>Chemokine signaling pathway</i>	46	<i>EGFR1 signaling pathway</i>	103
<i>Cytochrome, cyp</i>	51	<i>Complement and coagulation cascades</i>	51	<i>EPO receptor signaling</i>	20
<i>High mobility proteins, hmg</i>	11	<i>Cytosolic DNA-sensing pathway</i>	24	<i>Erk1-erk2 MAPK cascade</i>	71
<i>Homeo domain proteins, hom</i>	59	<i>Epithelial cell Helicobacter pylori</i>	31	<i>Fas pathway and stress induction</i>	28
<i>Heat shock proteins, hsp</i>	97	<i>Fc epsilon RI signaling pathway</i>	59	<i>FGF signaling pathway</i>	62
<i>Interferon, ifn</i>	36	<i>Fc gamma R-mediated phagocytosis</i>	38	<i>G protein signaling pathways</i>	17
<i>Immunoglobulins, igs</i>	45	<i>Hematopoietic cell lineage</i>	58	<i>Interleukin2</i>	50
<i>Interleukins, ils</i>	47	<i>Hepatitis C</i>	59	<i>Interleukin3</i>	65
<i>Kinases, kin</i>	60	<i>Herpes simple infection</i>	85	<i>Interleukin4</i>	38
<i>Macrophages, mac</i>	37	<i>HTLV-1 infection</i>	104	<i>Interleukin5</i>	43
<i>Major histocompatibility complex, mhc</i>	34	<i>Intestinal immune network IgA</i>	29	<i>Interleukin6</i>	61
<i>Myxovirus-induced proteins, mx</i>	6	<i>Influenza A</i>	86	<i>Interleukin7</i>	29
<i>Novel immune-type receptors, nitr</i>	17	<i>Jak-STAT signaling pathway</i>	23	<i>Interleukin9</i>	14
<i>Oncogenes</i>	45	<i>Malaria</i>	34	<i>Integrin-mediated cell adhesion</i>	49
<i>T cell receptor, tcr</i>	2	<i>MAPK signaling pathway</i>	99	<i>MAPK cascade</i>	20
<i>Toll-like receptors, tlr</i>	21	<i>Measles</i>	65	<i>MAPK signaling wikipathway</i>	36
<i>Tumor necrosis factor, tnf</i>	26	<i>Natural killer cell mediated cytotoxicity</i>	59	<i>P38 MAPK signaling pathway</i>	27
<i>Transcription factors, tra</i>	606	<i>NOD-like receptor signaling pathway</i>	38	<i>Proteasome degradation</i>	36
<i>VHSV-induced proteins, vig</i>	2	<i>RIG-I-like receptor signaling pathway</i>	42	<i>Senescence and autophagy</i>	42
<i>Zin finger factors, zin</i>	36	<i>T cell receptor signaling pathway</i>	60	<i>Signaling of hepatocyte growth</i>	26
<i>C-reactive protein, crp</i>	7	<i>TGF-beta signaling pathway</i>	39	<i>T-cell receptor wikipathway</i>	71
		<i>Toll-like receptor signaling pathway</i>	60	<i>TGFb receptor wikipathway</i>	93
		<i>NF-kappa B signaling pathway</i>	69	<i>TGFb signaling wikipathway</i>	26
		<i>PI3K-Akt signaling pathway</i>	73	<i>TNFa NFkB signaling</i>	111
		<i>Protein export</i>	19	<i>Toll-like receptor wikipathway</i>	53
		<i>Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum</i>	63	<i>Type II interferon signaling (IFNG)</i>	19
		<i>Ubiquitin-mediated proteolysis</i>	55		

514

515 **Table S2.** List of enriched KEGG pathways in the SVCV-infected group. ID: entry number;
 516 #genes: number of genes identified within that pathway. FDR: false positive rate.

ID	Name	#Genes	FDR
dre03010	Ribosome - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	106	3.12e-02
dre00010	Glycolysis / Gluconeogenesis - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	51	5.3e-01
dre03022	Basal transcription factors - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	26	5.37e-01
dre04620	Toll-like receptor signaling pathway - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	34	5.37e-01
dre01200	Carbon metabolism - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	83	5.37e-01
dre00630	Glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	22	5.37e-01
dre04060	Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	41	5.37e-01
dre01230	Biosynthesis of amino acids - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	49	5.37e-01
dre04370	VEGF signaling pathway - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	38	6.59e-01
dre04115	p53 signaling pathway - Danio rerio (zebrafish)	44	7.32e-01

517

518 **Table S3.** Primers used for quantitative reverse-transcription PCR.

Gene	Sequence	Access number
<i>ef1a</i>	Fw: 5'-CCACGTCGACTCCGGAAA-3' Rv: 5'-CGATTCCACCGCATTGTGTA-3'	AY422992.1
<i>SVCV-N</i>	Fw: 5'-AGCTTGCATTTGAGATCGACATT-3' Rv: 5'-GCATTATGCCGCTCCAAGAG-3'	U18101
<i>tlr3</i>	Fw: 5'-GAACAGAATGAAGCACATCAAACC-3' Rv: 5'-ACGGCACTGAATCCACCAC-3'	NM_212844
<i>nod2</i>	Fw: 5'-TTTAGCGGTGACGTCCAGAA-3' Rv: 5'-GCCTCATAGCCCAGTCACAA-3'	NM_001328044.1
<i>sting</i>	Fw: 5'-GTCGCTGCATTGAAACAGAA-3' Rv: 5'-CTTAACCCATGGAGCAGAGG-3'	XM_009306855.3
<i>infphi1</i>	Fw: 5'-AGTTGTGAAAAGCCACCTTCAGA-3' Rv: 5'-CATGTGTGACACTCAAGGATTGAC-3'	NM_207640
<i>rsad2</i>	Fw: 5'-ATTTGTGGAGGGCTTTCCTT-3' Rv: 5'-AGAGCTGTTGGCAGAATGGT-3'	NM_001020785
<i>gig2l</i>	Fw: 5'-GGGGTTTTGCCAGTCTAAGGA-3' Rv: 5'-GCCAGGTTTTCTGCAGTGG-3'	NM_001245989.1
<i>irf7</i>	Fw: 5'-CATTCAAACCACTTCAAGCAAC-3' Rv: 5'-GCTGGACTGAAGCAGGTATATTATTCT-3'	BC058298.1
<i>irf3</i>	Fw: 5'-CCCTGGAAACACGCTTTGA-3' Rv: 5'-GAGCCCACGCCTTGAATATG-3'	XM_017358468.2
<i>il1b</i>	Fw: 5'-GAACAGAATGAAGCACATCAAACC-3' Rv: 5'-ACGGCACTGAATCCACCAC-3'	NM_212844
<i>mxab</i>	Fw: 5'-GGTCTCTGGGAGTCGAAAAGG-3' Rv: 5'-AACTCTTTCCCGAGCTTTGGT-3'	AF_533769.1
<i>bdef2</i>	Fw: 5'-AATGTGCATAATGCCGAAGTACA-3' Rv: 5'-ACAACCATGGTGAGCAACAATATATT-3'	NM_001081554
<i>il6</i>	Fw: 5'-ATCCGAAATATCTGGAGACGAA-3' Rv: 5'-TCTGAAGGTTTGAGGAGAGGAG-3'	NM_001261449.1
<i>crp1</i>	FW: 5'-GCC TAC CGA ACA CCC GAC T-3' RV: 5'-GCA GGT TGA AAA ACG CC-3'	XM_693995.8
<i>crp2</i>	FW: 5'-TCT TCT GTT CCC GAC TG-3' RV: 5'-GGA TGA TCT CCC TTT TGG-3'	XM_005162877.4
<i>crp3</i>	FW: 5'-ATC CCA GTT ATG TTC AAA TCG-3' RV: 5'-AGC AGC TCC AAC CTG-3'	NM_001114915.2
<i>crp4</i>	FW: 5'-GAA AAG TGC TTC TGT TTA CAG-3' RV: 5'-CGA ACA AGA TGA CTT CCC-3'	NM_001040297.1
<i>crp6</i>	FW: 5'-GAA CTC AAT GTG TGG AGA C-3' RV: 5'-AGA TAG AAA CTT GCT GGA TTG-3'	XM_009297633.2
<i>crp7</i>	FW: 5'-CCA AAC TGC TAC CAG C-3' RV: 5'-AGA ATG ACT TCC CGC C-3'	NM_001102627.1

519

Fig.3 A,B

Fig.3

Fig.3

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.4A

Fig.4B

Highlights

- First ChIPseq-based study of SVCV-infected zebrafish
- Rapid increment of H3K4 methylation in promoters of immune-related gene promoters after SVCV infection
- Key inflammatory and antiviral genes showed transcriptional activation in correlation to gene promoter methylation
- C-reactive proteins genes exhibit the highest H3 methylation enrichment after 5 days of SVCV infection